

Theory of Superposition within quantum states, An Hypothetical answer

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Abstract—Our Quantum Approach relies on an hypothetical experiment were we interpret actual nature of reality within quantum mechanics and networks based on theoretical assumption of how nature of particle or properties of real data changes to imaginary due to superposition within multiple states.

Index Terms—Quantum Information, Quantum Entanglement, Hypothetical Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION: AN ASSUMPTION

Superposition of two sides of one coin and its theory: the Answer is simple, when a coin is tossed and either sides of coin i.e, heads or tails will be the call if we referred as "superposition of two sides" lets define in quantum physics, it means hypothetically answer may be percentage of 50-50, 40-60 or 70-30 i.e, tossing of heads or tails within desired quantum state but a rotation of coin and its spin explains answer in desired states always qualifies for an imaginary conclusion moreover, within the field of quantum mechanics, when we try to interpret what we quantifies it actually defines nature of reality.

II. UNDERSTANDING DETERMINISTIC QUANTUM APPROACH

A deterministic quantum approach always relays on respective principle for instance, a superposition of particle can exist in multiple quantum states at same time until it is quantified. The problem lies here i.e, due to Multiple states, if the superposition appears again in the previous state then nature of particle eventually changes to imaginary and moreover due to past state, entanglement happens in future state instead of desired state. our previous research work cited at [3] and its continuation referenced at [2], [4] resulted in understanding that

properties of real data has been changed to imaginary data due to superposition of qubits state which appears at same state twice.

III. CONCLUSION

We conclude that due to multiple quantum states and its superposition of qubits appears twice within same state resulted in change of properties of data towards imaginary and more over, according to [1] decoherence is unavoidable due to multiple states.

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